

ABOUT SOME LINGUGOGEOGRAPHICAL PROPERTIES OF PLACE NAMES (on the example of Jizzakh region)

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Abstract: The article examines some lingvogeographic features of place names on the example of Jizzakh region. Based on the main function and main purpose of the geographical name, the issues of interrelation of place and name and regional features of topoformants in the structure of names are studied. At the same time, toponymic analysis of the geographical name and its components, topoformants specializing in the creation of place names and their distinguishing features were studied. The appellate and oykonims formed on the basis of the

famous horses were studied with the help of concrete examples, and advanced scientific views on the field were described.

Keywords: appellation, geographical object, place name, topoformant, topothem, name and place connection, types of toponyms.

Introduction

In scientific works, a geographical name called a toponym is created in a specific language and is the product of a specific historical period and the spiritual property of the people. However, any place name is a word, it is expressed through language, and language is part of the vocabulary, but it is a specific and very different part of other lexical layers. In the words of the well-known scientist S. Karaev, “this difference is reflected in the longevity of toponyms, their multi-component, ie multi-component, the ability of appellatives (related horses) to participate in the creation of toponyms according to the internal laws of each language”[1].

Experts write that “geographical names were originally composed of simple cognate words in the early stages of language development. People simply referred to various objects as water, mountains, tugai, lakes, towns, and so on. Some of these cognate words have gradually become famous horses. For example, the ancient Turkic peoples called the great river "ox", "edil", "jayhun". These words later became a well-known name for rivers” [2].

The main function and main purpose of a geographical name is to clearly identify a particular place on this earth. It is known that the exact sciences do this work using coordinates, but to do it will require specialists with good skills and training. It is clear that not everyone can perform such a task in everyday life, so people preferred to express in words the easiest and most convenient way, that is, the surrounding objects. The natural environment that surrounds us, especially the geographical environment that is part of it, has served as a toponymic source for place names. In other words, “a toponymic source occurs at every step, and the main task should be to collect and classify place names in their original form». [3]

The study of the subject

So far, the lingvogeographic features of place names and their problems have been relatively little studied by geographers. Therefore, the study of lingvogeographic features of toponyms within a specific region or territorial-administrative unit and the definition of existing toponymic laws is of great theoretical and practical importance. This situation determines the relevance of the topic under study. Toponymic scientists H. Hasanov, AV Superanskaya, NG Mallitsky, AL Khromov, S. Karaev, T. Nafasov, Z. Dusimov, M. Mirakmalov were used in this research.

Goals and objectives of the work

The main purpose of the research is to study some lingvogeographical features of place names and the main function and main purpose of the geographical name, the relationship between place and name, as well as regional differences of topoformants in the composition of names. The following tasks will

be performed during the research: 1) toponymic analysis of the place name and its components; 2) study of topoformants specializing in the creation of place names and their distinguishing features; 3) study of oykonims formed on the basis of appeals and famous horses; 4) promotion of advanced scientific ideas in the field.

The main part

Any geographical name is a product of understanding the world, in which the daily life, lifestyle, culture, customs of people in a particular region are reflected. Consequently, names that are the product of social necessity reflect the process by which humanity perceives objective events in a geographical environment. This process is, of course, closely linked to people's social life, national and spiritual values, ethnic composition of the local population, migration, language history and the natural-geographical environment that surrounds them.

Well-known theorist of toponymy AV Superanskaya wrote about it: "By expressing geographical names with the word toponymy, we emphasize that they are close (compatible) with other famous names, for example, anthroponymy, ethnonymy, zoonymy, etc. Geographical names are extremely lively, long-lived. They can change their content and pronunciation not only in the region of origin, but also beyond the range of the language, assimilate into other languages and change depending on the local geographical features of the place". [4]

The correct spelling of geographical names is a very important and complex issue. Importantly, if a letter in a geographical name is misspelled, it can become a completely different toponym as a result of phonetic changes. The complexity of the problem of spelling place names correctly is that they are created in different languages and are actually written according to the rules of those languages. Changes in both pronunciation and spelling may occur when switching to other languages.

Z. Dusimov, who studied Khorezm toponymy, wrote: "It is impossible to say the same about all suffixes in toponyms. In the Uzbek language there are suffixes of the type "-obod", "-iston", "-kent (kand, kat)", which always make place names. Therefore, it is appropriate to call such suffixes toponymic affixes (topoaffixes) [5]. In national toponymy, the affix "-s" is a topoformant that specializes in creating many place names. It signifies an unknown plurality, respect, emphasis on an idea, concretization of an abstract concept, generality, repetition, and has no effect on the meaning of a word. [6] For example, the center of Arnasay district is called the Victory Town. The toponym is based on the Arabic word "winner". The word "winner" means "winner", "victor". It is named after the great people who achieved great success in the development of the Jizzakh desert, who succeeded in turning the centuries-old desert into a garden.

Professor S. Karaev believes that the emergence of toponyms using the affix "-s" is associated with the settlement of nomadic peoples in the next 200-300 years, and justifies this by the fact that most of them are ethnonyms. The scholar determined that the affix -s is used to create toponyms that are associated only with people (Arabs, beys, rich, jewelers, lords, etc.) and that this feature in "-s" is specific to all Turkic peoples. [7] For example, there is no doubt that the name of Beklar village in Sharof Rashidov district was based on an ethnonym. Another

scholar, B. Urinbaev, commented on it: "One of the descendants of the bell tribe of the bell tribe, which is part of the Uzbek people, is called beks. The mangits have a ball called a beggar, and the mirishkis have a ball called beglar. [8]

The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, one of the main scientific and reliable sources, describes the word bek as follows: "Representatives of a special military unit in the service of the khan in the ancient Turkic peoples. They had great privileges and formed a class of high military aristocrats. " [9] Thus, it has been proven that the word beks has evolved from an ethnonym to a oykon. Turkologist K. Musaev found that "in Turkish toponymic areas, the suffixes -li and -lik form more active toponyms than other affixes." [10] The scholar found that although the suffix "-li" did not have a distinct lexical meaning, it did specialize in making place names as a sign of the existence and abundance of that object when combined with formants. Examples of such place names are Molali, Tepali (Forish district), Almali, Tutli (Gallaorol district), Tangili (Bakhmal district), Tolli, Urikli (Zamin district).

There is a village called Alamli along the Tuyatortar canal, which passes through the territory of Bakhmal district. Naturally, the history of the origin of the name of the village has interested many scholars. In particular, H. Hasanov narrated the following legend about the name: When the boy took pity on them and went to the khan and said, "Is this the end of the trouble, stop being tired," the angry khan slaughtered the boy there. The people called the village a memory of the tragedy. " [11]

Well-known scholar S. Karaev gave a different definition to the word "alam": alam (Arabic) - rags hanging on the branches of trees growing on the steps of saints or on sticks stuck in the graves of martyrs. Meaning (from Arabic) means "flag". The names of the places Alam, Alamdor, Alamli mean "the tomb of the saints" or "the place where the martyr is buried". There are also many legends about why the channel was named Tuyatortar. For example, Tora Nafasov, who studied the toponymy of southern Uzbekistan, wrote that there was a Tuyatortar ditch in the Kasan district of Kashkadarya region, and described the name as follows: The rope was moved and turned by a camel. The water tank mounted on the chute was much larger, so it was turned with great force. It is so called because of the movement of the camel [12].

Mulberry has long been cultivated in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, as a fruit tree. Hence a number of names associated with the name of this fruit tree. For example, in the territory of Jizzakh region: Koshtut, Yakkatut, Yonboshtut, Tutak, Tutli. According to experts, "NV Goryaev and AG Preobrazhensky, who created the etymological dictionary of the Russian language, considered the word mulberry to be Arabic. Other scholars, such as E. Berneker, considered it to belong to the Oromo language, H. Peterson, O. Schroeder to belong to the Sanskrit language. According to scholars, the word mulberry passed from Sanskrit to Persian, and from there to Turkish, Russian, Armenian and other languages. Nowadays, the word mulberry is present in all Turkic and Iranian languages, it was known to the peoples of the Eastern countries BC as a food tree for feeding the cultural tree, silkworm, and was used in their language with the same sound

structure. Mulberry is a place where mulberry trees grow, mulberry trees ». The names of tribes, clans and other ethnic groups formed by ethno-okonyms using the affix "-li" in the study area can also be included in this list. For example, Baymoqli, Bag'anali, Oytamgali, Soloqli, Tuyakli, Taraqli, Chomichli, Chaparashli, Erganakli and others.

In the territory of Jizzakh region there are a lot of oykonims with the suffix "-lik". Examples of such are the names of urban mahallas, such as Jewelry, Butchery, Akkurgan, Yakhtan, Uratepalik. The Uratepalik mahalla in Jizzakh was named after Uratepa (now Istaravshan, Sughd Province, Tajikistan) and the surrounding population. According to historical sources, the people of the mahalla moved to Jizzakh 250-300 years ago.

The suffix "-on" and "yon", which express the plural, are also included in the toponyms of the region. According to S.Karaev, they are members of a certain ethnic group (Arab, Kyrgyz, Kazakh), ethnic group (China, Turkon, Qarluqon), belonging to a certain profession (Mirzoyon, Khojagon, Tarkhanon), connection with this or that profession (Ahangaron, Sozangaron, Sarrafon), denoting religious affiliation (Buddhism, Christianity, Mughan). [13] Indeed, in order to determine whether the suffix "-on" and "-i" refer to a particular ethnic group, we refer to the following example. I have an ethno-village named Karakhan in Forish district. The people of this village consider themselves to be the descendants of the Karakhan saint, known as the Holy Father. The tomb of the saint is located in the city of Taraz in the Republic of Kazakhstan, and until 1936 this city was known as Avliyota.

Another well-known scholar Tora Nafasov also commented on this ethnonym: "Karakhanids are an ancient Turkic people. In fact, the Karakhanid state was founded in 927-1212 in East Turkestan, and then the head of the Turkish state, which also conquered the lands between the Amu Darya, was Abdukarim Sotuq Bugrakhan. In 996-999 he subjugated Movarounnahr. The territorial and political-social group associated with this dynasty was called the Karakhanids. Later, they merged with the ancient settled Turkic peoples. They can be considered as an example of the ancestors of the Karakhanid period (X-XII centuries).

Toponym-forming affixes such as "-cha", "-i", "-lar" in place names were studied by T.Nafasov on the example of toponymy of Kashkadarya region. [14] The formation of toponyms by adding these affixes to topoformants can also be analyzed in the case of Jizzakh region. For example, there is a village called Kudukcha in Zaamin district. Due to the lack of running water in the rural area, locals often drink water from wells. Experts write that the well does not mean "small well", but means a village (place) with a well. Indeed, there are many wells in this village. Another scholar, B. Urinbaev, wrote that the name of the village was an ethnonym.

The affix "-ot", which makes up the toponym, appeared in two different ways: one is Arabic and the other is Sogdian. In addition, the affix "-t" also means plural in ancient Turkic and Mongolian languages. The suffix -ak as a topoaffix is a sign of the smallness of the geographical object, which formed many place names in the territory of Jizzakh region using topoformants. For example, the

original form of the name Jizzakh was Dizak, which means "small fortress" in the ancient Sogdian language. Place names such as Kochak, Fashtak, Fojak in Forish district were also created with the help of the -ak suffix.

According to experts, the affix "-ak" is a product of the Sogdian language and is one of the oldest lexical layers of the toponymy of Jizzakh region. Sogdian names are more common in the mountainous areas of the study area (Yangiabad, Zaamin, Bakhmal, Gallaaral, Forish districts). The reason is that these areas were part of the historical region of Ustrushna in the early Middle Ages. A.L. Khromov, a Russian scholar who has studied the toponymy of Yagnob, concludes that "often the affix" -ak "is added independently of the main toponym, sometimes it is directly related to the finished toponym, and in such cases the place of the new name is smaller than the previous one." [15]

Elements of the Sogdian language are quite significant in the structure of modern regional toponymy, therefore, toponymic data is a valuable and important source in their study. There are also geographical names in the region that, although the words or affixes in them belong to the Sogdian language, the toponym was not created directly by the Sogdians. These types of toponyms are formed from words and affixes transferred from Sogdian, Uzbek or Persian-Tajik to Uzbek, which can be called structurally hybrid names. For example, Yangikent oykonim in Zarbdor district can be called a hybrid name. The name was given to a new settlement that emerged during the development of the Jizzakh desert. The new word in the name of the place - "not before", "recently built", and kent - in the ancient Sogdian language - means "city", "village". Yangikent - created as a result of the development of the desert - means "new settlement".

Geographical names, the genesis of which is used in both Persian-Tajik and Uzbek languages, using the affix "-zor", which is characteristic of Iranian languages, are more productive in the toponymy of the region. Toponyms such as Almazor (Jizzakh city), Bogzor (Dustlik district), Pakhtazor (Mirzachul district), Gulzor (Arnasay district), Chilanzar (Zaamin district), Lolazor (Zafarabad district), Uzumzor (Pakhtakor district) with the help of the plural -zor suffix (phytooykonims). Such toponyms are more common in the northern plain part of the province. All of them are administratively created, ie in the "cabinet". The place names in the desert part of the region are not very lexically diverse. Because if the terrain is flat, if there are no natural boundaries, the toponym will be less.

The name of one of the villages in the territory of Zaamin district is Chilanzar - chilon (jelon) - a type of thorny tree, the fruit of which resembles jiida, is also used in medicine, sometimes called Gurgon jiida. For this reason, Chilanzar is actually a place where a chilon (jelon) tree grows a lot. NG Mallitsky, on the other hand, misinterpreted Chilanzar, the name of one of the largest residential areas in Tashkent, a metro station, and one of the city's districts, as a maple grove, meaning "a place with a lot of maple trees." [16]

Experts have found that place names with the suffix "-obod" were created long ago. For example, the researcher of the history of Persian languages AL Khromov writes that in Movarounnahr in the VII-VIII centuries the names of prosperous words appeared. [17] The word has long been a symbol and has always

been the last component of nouns. Tora Nafasov described the word "-obod" as "the transition to a sedentary life, land development, the creation and growth of agricultural culture, the emergence of large settlements, paving the way for the word obod to take on a new meaning." First of all, the word obod meant a place mastered by human activity. Then he wrote correctly that "the place of prosperity", "aul", "village" also increased.

The principle of naming the new settlements created due to the development of the Jizzakh desert was followed. such names appeared. Such names indicate that the word "-obod" is still very active in making names. In Jizzakh there is a very old neighborhood called Khayrabad. It should be noted that the formation of the place name by adding the word "-obod" to the word good is not typical of modern times. The interpretation of Khayrabad as a benevolent neighborhood cannot be considered scientifically justified. However, the locals describe my toponym as a place where "goodness", "charity", "generosity", "charity" flourished.

According to Professor B. Urinbaev, "the name of the mahalla is actually related to the Arabic word harobot. Ruin means "tavern", "in a t-shirt", "pub", "a place of entertainment" or "a place where Sufis moan and worship". Academician A.Muhammadjanov, who conducted archeological research in the Jizzakh oasis in the 50s and 60s of the last century, explained the name of the mahalla as follows: In the works of the 13th century Arab geographer Yaqut Hamawi, the words khan and tim (surrounded by a wall and covered with rain) in the Khorasanian language were closely related in meaning and function.

It is well known that place names, which are the most advanced type of famous horses, are grammatically composed of one or more components. Typical toponyms, including oikonoms, consist of two or more components, while toponyms consisting of a single word can be names in which any component is omitted. Most of the place names consisting of lexical units are related names, ie appellations - geographical and socio-economic terms, professional lexemes, plant - animal names, as well as well-known horses, ie onyms - tribal names (ethnonyms), human nicknames. (anthroponyms) and others.

Due to the fact that the research focuses on the names of settlements, the region can be divided into two major groups on the basis of its composition:

1. The oykonims on which the appeals are based. The names in this group are made up of different related horses. Given the diversity of related horses created by oykonims, some of the appeals that are still more active in making names have been identified:

a) natural geographical terms: adir - Adirabad (Zarbdor district), ariq - Uchariq (Jizzakh city), arna - Arnasay (Arnasay district), bulak - Egizbulak (Forish district), boktar - Boktaryo'l (Zaamin district), jar - Jamonjar (Bakhmal district), josha - Joshali (Forish district), kamar - Kamarli (Bakhmal district), kechuv - Ettikechuv (Zaamin district), tepa - Uchtepa (Sh. Rashidov district) and others;

b) socio-economic terms: band - Khanbandi (Forish district), bek - Beklar (Jizzakh district), varg - Vargin (Yangiabad district), dargat - Dargat (Jizzakh district), kent - Nushkent (Bakhmal district), yom - Yom (Zaamin district), kurgan

- Khanimkurgan (Gallaorol district), garden - Chorbog (Forish district), cemetery - Sofimozor (Zaamin district), bazaar - Kohnabozor (Forish district), etc. ;

c) professional terms: yamchi - Yomchi (Forish district), jeweler - Jewelry (Jizzakh city), butcher - Butcher (Jizzakh city), soap maker - Soapmaking (Jizzakh city), pakhtakor - Pakhtakor (Pakhtakor district), chemist - Chemist (Jizzakh) and others.

2. Oykonyms formed on the basis of famous horses. The names of such settlements are often based on anthroponyms and ethnonyms.

a) names of people, nicknames, nicknames, proportions, names of settlements derived from surnames in later periods are called anthropoikonyms. According to S.Koraev: "The most accurate and perfect type of the model of anthropoikonyms grammatically corresponding to the Uzbek language consists of anthroponyms and geographical terms. For example, Yunusabad, Chingizkent, Akmalabad and others. Such perfect anthroponyms are also found in the region. For example, Suvonabad (Pakhtakor district), Eshmatovul (Zaamin district) and others. "The transfer of human names to any settlement is also connected with social realities such as private ownership, development of new lands, construction of new settlements. It is rare for them to be named after other toponymic groups, but it is a phenomenon. " [18].

b) The names of settlements, tribes, as well as settlements formed on the basis of the names of different ethnic units are called ethno-okonyms. Ethno-names play an important role in the toponymy of the region, and through them it is possible to find out in which regions the representatives of the ethnic group lived. Some ethno-names that appear on the map of the region as place names: Bolgali, Barlos, Jaloyir, Kaltatay, Naiman, Oytamgali, Uymovut, Sherkangli, Chaparashli, Kangli, Orokli and others. The transfer of ethnonyms to the name of neighborhood, village, district, city is a common phenomenon in the toponymy of Central Asia, and they are part of the toponymy of all regions.

It is also possible to find in the region under study the names of small geographical objects, ie microtoponyms. One of the basic laws of toponymy is that microtoponyms are later transformed into macrotoponyms, because the name of any dead geographical object was originally a small place name.

Conclusion

Analyzing some lingvogeographical features of place names, the following conclusions can be made:

a) The transfer of names belonging to different groups to each other often occurs in adjacent objects. As you can see, the name for a new geographic object is not searched remotely, the name of the adjacent object is selected as the name of the object being named.

b) The transition of geographical names from one type to another is a sign of the universality of toponyms, and this phenomenon can be called a clear expression of the high spiritual wealth of the people.

c) there is no "Chinese wall" between different toponyms (hydronyms, oronyms, phytonyms, etc.), the names of streams, streams, lakes (hydronyms), the

names of relief forms (oronyms), the names of different plants (phytonyms) possible.

g) the linguogeographic features of place names do not recognize administrative boundaries, which indicates that they were formed over long historical periods;

d) study of linguogeographic features of toponyms and promotion of advanced scientific ideas in the field are of great scientific and practical importance.

References.

- [1] Qoraev S. Toponymy. -T .; 2006, - p. 6.
- [2] Hasanov H. The secret of geographical names. - T.; 1985, - p.22.
- [3] Popov A.I. Geographic names. -M.; 1965, -p.10.
- [4] A. V. Superanskaya What is toponymy. -M.; 1985 - p. 99.
- [5] Dusimov Z. On the issue of making toponyms. -T.; Uzbek language and literature, 1980. № 2.
- [6] Karimov S.A., Buriev S.N. Uzbek toponymy is developing. -T .; 2006. -b.59.
- [7] Karaev S. Experience of studying toponymy of Uzbekistan. Abstract of the thesis. dis. on sois. Cand. Phil. sciences. -T.; 1969.- p.144.
- [8] Urinboev B. Interpretation of Jizzakh toponyms. -Samarkand, 2007. -p.19.
- [9] In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 1, -T.; 2000. - p. 680.
- [10] Musaev K.M. Lexicology of Turkic languages. -M., 1984. - p.188.
- [11] Hasanov H. From the history of Central Asian place names. -T.; 1965. - p.31.
- [12] Nafasov T. Annotated dictionary of toponyms of Uzbekistan. -T.; 1988. - p.181.
- [13] Karaev S. On indicators of plurality in toponyms of Uzbekistan. -M .; Journal Soviet Turkology, 1979. № 5.
- [14] Nafasov T. Toponyms of the Kashkadarya region. Abstract of the thesis. dis. on sois. uch. step. Cand. Phil. sciences. -T.; 1968.
- [15] Khromov A.L. Essays on toponymy and microtoponymy of Tajikistan. - Dushanbe. 1975. - p.13-14.
- [16] Mallitsky N.G. Tashkent mahalla and mausa. -T.; 1927.
- [17] Khromov A.L. On the structural features of Iranian toponymy. Maverannahr in the period of the IX-XIII centuries. Eastern philology. issue 3. -Dushanbe. 1974. -p. 3.
- [18] Xakimov K.M. Toponymy. -T.; 2016. - b. 368.
- [19] Saparov K., Rasulov A., Nizamov A. Problems of regionalization of geographical names // Innovations in science, society, education. 2021. 119-121.